

ISic0640

I.Sicily inscription 0640

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

plaque

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Centuripae

Place of origin (modern)

Centuripe

Provenance

Found by Dr Pr. Cacia 'in un suo podere'

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Centuripe, private collection (P. Cacia)

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI332878

1. Πουβλειλί-

2. α □ Ἀγάθιν □

3. χρηστά □ χαῖρε □

4. ἔζησεν ἔτη □ λ□γ' #⁵⁶

5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644882

EDCS 64800567

PHI 332878

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1994.0763

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 44.0746

Manganaro, G. 1994. Iscrizioni, epigrafi ed epigrammi in Greco della Sicilia orientale di epoca romana. *Mélanges de l'École Française de Rome: Antiquité.* 106: 79-118. At 85 no.3b

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